

By-laws of the International Network of Open Science and Scholarship Communities (INOSC) Foundation

Version 1.2 (November 2025)

Denomination and domicile

Article 1

1. The Foundation is denominated **International Network of Open Science and Scholarship Communities** (hereinafter referred to as INOSC)
2. INOSC is registered at the Dutch Chamber of Commerce under number 88539989.

Objectives

Article 2

1. The vision of INOSC is that local Open Science and Scholarship Communities (hereinafter referred to as OSCs) are key actors in facilitating the transition to Open Science and Open Scholarship worldwide.
2. OSCs are learning communities that invite and unite Open Science and Open Scholarship newcomers and experts, and enable them to actively shape the transition to Open Science and Open Scholarship.
3. The objectives of INOSC are to make the network of OSCs
 - a. bigger (i.e., inspire and support scholars around the globe to start their own local OSC);
 - b. better (i.e., help local OSCs to achieve their goals and become (more) sustainable); and
 - c. stronger (i.e., provide input on behalf of OSCs to (inter)national stakeholders on Open Science and Open Scholarship policies, infrastructures, and services).

Administration

Article 3

1. INOSC consists of **OSC Representatives** (Article 4), an **INOSC Board** (Article 5) and **INOSC Initiatives** (Article 11).
2. INOSC governs a registry of OSCs affiliated to INOSC (see Article 7.4e).
3. Aspiring OSCs are added to the registry after a positive decision by the INOSC Board, following the procedures described in the INOSC Starter Kit (www.StartYourOSC.com).

OSC Representatives

Article 4

1. Each OSC is represented within INOSC by one individual, the **OSC Representative** (hereinafter referred to as Representative).
2. Each OSC determines its own procedure for selecting the Representative of their OSC (e.g., by elections amongst OSC members).
3. Representatives are responsible for
 - a. the communication between INOSC and the OSC they represent. This communication includes, but is not limited to, information about events and elections; and
 - b. voting on behalf of the OSC they represent on INOSC matters. This includes, but is not limited to, elections and decisions that concern the whole of INOSC.
 - i. In voting, each Representative, and thus each OSC, has one vote.
4. Representatives do not pay fees to INOSC, nor are they paid by INOSC.

INOSC Board

Article 5

1. Subject to the limitations according to these statutes, the **INOSC Board** (hereinafter referred to as Board) is in charge of managing INOSC and is legally responsible for INOSC.
2. The Board decides in all cases not governed by the law or these statutes.
3. The Board consists of six people, called Board members, who serve a two-year term.

Board: Formation

Article 6

1. The Board is formed by means of annual elections.
2. Three Board member positions are open for elections annually.
 - a. To enable this, three Board members in the first Board will serve for one year instead of the default two-year term (but can be re-elected; see Article 6.3c).
 - b. In a situation where less than three current Board members stay on the Board, more than three positions may be opened for elections to make sure the Board has six Board members. The Board will in this case determine internally who of the new Board members will serve a one- or two-year term.
 - c. When not all spots in the board are taken after elections, it is possible for OSC members to apply for becoming a board member throughout the year as well, and not only during the formal election process.
3. All members of OSCs are eligible to be elected onto the Board.

- a. OSC members can self-nominate.
 - b. For OSCs that do not offer membership, eligibility of individuals for the Board will be determined by the Representative of that OSC.
 - c. Current Board members may run for re-election as long as they do not serve more than two consecutive terms (i.e., four consecutive years).
 - i. As a result, the first three Board members that serve a one-year term (see Article 6.2a) can serve no longer than three (instead of four) consecutive years when re-elected.
4. The Board is responsible for promoting diversity among its members (see also Article 7.3di).
- a. If after elections the Board would comprise of members affiliated with the same OSC, and there were other eligible candidates, a candidate with fewer - but at least one - votes and affiliated with an OSC not already presented in the Board should be given precedence.
 - b. If after elections the Board consists of a majority of members affiliated with a single country, and there were other eligible candidates, a candidate with fewer - but at least one - votes and from a country not already presented in the Board should be given precedence.
5. Representatives will elect Board members.
- a. If the number of candidates in a Board election is **equal to (or lower than)** the number of positions available, there will be no elections. All candidates will automatically become a member of the Board.
 - b. If there are **no candidates** in a Board election, the Board may continue to operate with at least three members as long as the responsibilities of the Board can be divided over the Board members (see Article 7)
 - i. The term for remaining Board members ends with the next elections. However, for reasons of continuity, these Board members are allowed to extend their terms of service.
 - ii. In case there is an insufficient number of current Board members that agrees to remain on the Board to meet the conditions laid out in Article 6.5b, then the Board should dissolve INOSC (see Article 13).
6. If an OSC Representative is elected to serve on the Board, the OSC this person was representing needs to select a new OSC Representative (see Article 4)
7. If a Board member leaves the Board before the end of their term (see Article 10), the remaining Board members decide whether to
- a. hold an *ad hoc* election for the vacant position. This position will then be filled by a newly elected Board member for the remainder of the term of the Board member who stepped down; or
 - b. continue and distribute the tasks of the Board member who stepped down over the remaining Board members, provided that the conditions in Article 6.5b are met
 - i. In this case, the vacant Board position will be filled in the subsequent annual election. After this election, the Board determines internally which new Board members will serve a one- or two-year term, if a one-year term

is necessary to warrant that half of the Board can be renewed upon a subsequent election.

8. If a board member is unavailable during a longer period of time, the standing board members can appoint someone in a temporary board position (interim). For example when a board member has personal circumstances for a longer period of time (sick, sickness in the family, delivery of a baby, parental leave etc.)

Board: Roles and Responsibilities

Article 7

1. The Board has a Chair, a Vice-chair, a Secretary, and a Treasurer.
2. The Chair's responsibilities include but are not limited to:
 - a. overseeing regularly scheduled Board meetings, an annual meeting with the Advisory Board (see Article 7.12), and calling special meetings as necessary;
 - b. preparing the agenda of Board meetings;
 - c. determining Board decision-making procedures (see Article 9);
 - d. working in partnership with Representatives and Initiatives leads to make sure resolutions are carried out and issues addressed by the Board as needed; and
 - e. coordinating the annual evaluation and reporting of INOSC (see Article 7.3d).
3. The Vice-chair's responsibilities include but are not limited to:
 - a. understanding the responsibilities of the Chair and being able to take over those responsibilities when needed;
 - b. checking that action has been taken following decisions at previous Board meetings;
 - c. receiving all communication from Representatives and INOSC Initiatives to the Board and relaying as necessary; and
 - d. ensuring the production of an annual report on Board activities and decisions.
 - i. The annual report should include a statement on how the Board promoted diversity among its members.
4. The Secretary's responsibilities include but are not limited to:
 - a. scheduling Board meetings, an annual meeting with the Advisory Board, and other special meetings, as requested by Board members;
 - b. sending Board members an invitation to and agenda for Board meetings;
 - c. ensuring that someone is assigned to and takes minutes during all official Board meetings;
 - d. circulating Board meeting minutes; and
 - e. governing the registry of OSCs affiliated to INOSC
5. The Treasurer's responsibilities include but are not limited to:
 - a. ensuring the production of financial reports when required and the preparation of the annual budget; and
 - b. presenting the budget to the Board for approval, and answering questions from the Board, Representatives, and the general public about the budget and finances.

6. After every election, the Board decides internally how these roles will be distributed among its members.
7. The Board may assign additional tasks and roles amongst its members.
8. The Board is responsible for elections.
9. The Board oversees and coordinates the INOSC Initiatives (see Article 11).
10. The Board periodically informs all Representatives of its activities during INOSC meetings.
11. The Board reviews INOSC's vision, aims, and values at least every two years, or whenever they see fit before that.
12. The Board is guided by an Advisory Board.
 - a. The size and constitution of the Advisory Board is determined by the Board
 - b. The Advisory Board provides feedback at least once a year on the plans and activity of the Board.

Board: Meetings

Article 8

1. The Board shall meet regularly and at least once a year or as often as the Chair or other Board members deem appropriate.
2. Board meetings can only take place when at least half of the Board members are present.
3. A Board member may be represented at the meeting by a fellow Board member authorised by them in writing.
 - a. A Board member may represent a maximum of one co-Board member at a meeting.
 - b. If a Board member represents a co-Board member at a meeting, the representing Board member should make this clear at the beginning of the meeting.

Board: Decision-making

Article 9

1. Each Board member has one vote. Insofar as these articles do not provide otherwise, board decisions are taken by an absolute majority of the votes cast at the meeting. Blank votes are considered to have not been cast.
2. In the event of a tie, the vote should be submitted to the OSC Representatives.
3. The Chair determines the voting procedure.
 - a. Voting is non-anonymous by default. In cases where at least one Board member expresses the wish to vote anonymously, this request will be implemented.
 - b. In the absence of the Chair, the Vice-chair can determine the voting procedure.

4. Board decisions may be taken outside a meeting, provided that all Board members are given the opportunity to vote and have all stated that they do not oppose this method of decision-making.

Board: Termination of membership

Article 10

1. The term of a Board member shall be terminated if any of the following conditions exist:
 - a. the Board member dies;
 - b. the Board member resigns;
 - c. the Board member is dismissed by a general vote by the other Board members. In this case, an unanimous vote is required amongst the other Board members; or
 - d. in the case of dismissal based on article 2:298 of the Civil Act (Dutch: Burgelijk Wetboek).
2. The entire Board can be dismissed by a general vote of the Representatives. In this case, a 75% majority vote is required to dismiss the Board and ad-hoc elections are organised.
 - a. The dismissed Board is responsible for organising these ad-hoc elections.
 - b. Ad-hoc elections should take place within six months after the vote that resulted in the Board being dismissed.
 - c. To these ad-hoc elections the same conditions and procedures apply as when the first INOSC board was instantiated (see Article 6.21 and Article 6.3ci).

INOSC Initiatives

Article 11

1. **INOSC Initiatives** (hereinafter referred to as Initiatives) are specific projects within the scope and mission of INOSC.
2. Initiatives can be proposed by Representatives to the Board:
 - a. Individual OSC members can suggest Initiatives to their Representatives.
 - b. OSCs that do not offer membership will determine their own procedure for proposing Initiatives to their Representatives.
 - c. Each OSC determines its own procedure for handling these proposals.
3. The Board is responsible for making sure that Initiatives are within the scope and mission of INOSC (see Article 7.9). Therefore,
 - a. Initiatives should be approved by the Board; and
 - b. Initiative leads should regularly report to the Board on their progress.
4. Initiatives can, in addition to its proposing OSC member(s), include as many OSC members and non-members as required for the specific project.

Modification of statutes

Article 12

1. The Board may modify the statutes. A decision thereto requires a two third majority vote in a meeting attended by at least two third of all Board members (either in person or represented).
2. The modification shall be registered by a notary. Each Board member is entitled to perform such registration.
3. The Board members shall ensure that any modification is registered with the Chamber of Commerce.

Dissolution

Article 13

1. The Board is authorised to decide to dissolve INOSC; this decision thereto requires a two third majority vote of a meeting attended by all Board members (either in person or represented).
2. A Board decision to terminate INOSC shall include a decision on the beneficiary of any financial balance after repayment of all debts. In any other case the settlor shall decide on the beneficiary of any financial balance. The beneficiary of the financial balance shall comply as much as possible to objectives similar to those as defined in these statutes.
3. After the termination, the settlement shall be by the Board members, unless the Board decides to appoint a third party as settlor.
4. All formal documents related to the terminated foundation shall be kept by a person appointed by the settlor, during a period as defined by Dutch law.

Visualisation of INOSC structure

